

Newsletter EURCAW-Poultry-SFA

26 June 2026, Edition 16

Questions to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (Q2E)

All Q2E answers are available [online](#).

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2025-011: [Second stunning in broilers](#).

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2026-002: [Broiler fasting](#).

 Q2E-Poultry-SFA-2026-004: Stocking densities in poultry (ongoing)

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→ The Q2E webform is available online [here](#) or <https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/DSL/QuerywebformIQ3/questionnaire.htm>

→ You can download [here](#) the webform in PDF to prepare your Q2E submission.

2nd EURCAW-Poultry-SFA Roadshow, Spain

The second EURCAW-Poultry-SFA Roadshow was organized by the Spanish Centre partners in Madrid on May 27th 2026.

In total **20 participants**, from the main turkey producing regions, **7 observers** from the central **Competent Authority** and **3 EURCAW-Poultry-SFA** members attended this event.

This roadshow was focused on the topic turkey from farm to fork. Turkey outputs from the Centre were presented among EFSA reports, and case studies from the participants were discussed..

The presentation is available: [here](#) in Spanish and [here](#) in English.

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Highlights

★ New video: focus on turkey output!

A new video is available online: *Focus on turkey output: on farm, during transport and at the time of killing.*

The video is available [here](#).

The slideshow with links is available [here](#)

For more information take a look at the turkey sub-page [here](#).

★ New Indicator Factsheet: Use of enrichment in broilers

Providing broiler farms with effective environmental enrichments, meaning those capable of stimulating interest and being genuinely used by the animals, can promote the expression of species-specific behaviours, increase locomotor activity, and improve opportunities for exploration and occupation, thereby contributing to animal welfare. The assessment of the effectiveness of environmental enrichments is included, either directly or indirectly, in several welfare assessment protocols. However, these tools are generally designed to evaluate the overall welfare of the farm through animal-based, resource-based, and management-based indicators, and do not always allow for a specific assessment of environmental enrichments. EURCAW-Poultry-SFA has developed a specific protocol for *assessing environmental enrichments in broilers*. However, further investigation is still needed to define assessment methods that are more efficient, reliable, and applicable to different housing systems.

The factsheet is available [here](#). Take a look at the broiler chicken web-page [here](#).

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★ Third physical meeting of the 4 EURCAWs

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During 10 and 11 June 2026, The 4 EURCAWs met **physically in Rome** at the Italian Ministry of Health. The event was organized by the Italian colleagues (IZSAM) of the EURCAW Ruminants and Equines. **43 members** of the 4 EURCAWs were attending. The event was the occasion in the morning of the first day to work in subgroups on ongoing tasks of the 4 EURCAWs such as training and communication, and to exchange ideas and key strategic actions on transversal topics like networking, improving information flow toward targets, or technical studies, during a world Café session in the afternoon. The morning of the second day was dedicated to an open discussion on the key challenges and strategic priorities for the next EURCAWs' Work Programmes.

Info

★ Translations

Translations

[Dutch](#)

[French](#)

[German](#)

[Italian](#)

[Spanish](#)

[Polish](#)

If you are employed by a Competent Authority and willing to proof-read pre-translated factsheets using automatic translations into your native language, please contact us:

info@eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu

★ Are you aware of a good practice?

One of our activities in EURCAW-Poultry-SFA is to continuously search for examples of good practices that promote poultry and rabbit welfare, either on farm or at the slaughterhouse. Examples of good practices already described can be found on our website.

If you have suggestions for farms, slaughterhouses, specific equipment, practices, inspection procedures, etc that demonstrate or result in improved animal welfare, please do not hesitate to contact us: info@eurcaw-poultry-sfa.eu.

For more information take a look at the Good Practices sub-pages [broiler chicken](#), [laying hen](#), [turkey](#), [rabbit](#).

★ Follow us on LinkedIn!

Don't miss the latest from the EU Reference Centre for the Welfare of Poultry and small farmed animals!

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurcaw-poultry-sfa>

★ Subscribe to our Newsletter

 Want to stay in the loop on Poultry and Rabbit welfare in the EU? Be the first to receive:

- New publications
- Answers to Question to EURCAW-Poultry-SFA
- Info on upcoming events and resources

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